

A System for Energy Measurement on Accelerators (SEMA)

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Abstract

The fastest supercomputer in 2016 consumed over 17MW for a mere 33 Petaflops of performance. This makes energy efficiency a crucial obstacle to overcome in order to make Exascale computing a reality. Over 50% of the performance of this supercomputer is due to the presence of accelerators or coprocessors that are designed to do certain kind of mathematical operations in an energy efficient manner. Currently, accelerators such as NVIDIA GPGPUs and Intel Xeon Phi dominate this market. However, with the addition of FPGAs from Altera and Xilinx in HPC clusters, more options for accelerators are becoming available. Furthermore, several EU funded projects, including the Centre of Excellence and FETHPC projects such as ESCAPE, READEX, ESiWACE investigate HPC systems consisting of accelerators for Exascale-related applications. The dominance of such devices for energy efficient computing makes it crucial to understand the relationship between power consumption, performance and application code in order to exploit them in the most effective manner.

The measurement of power consumption is supported at different levels of accuracy by different vendors through their platforms. However, they lack any standardized metrics between them making it difficult to compare them directly. Further, the accuracy they support is at a coarse level making it impossible to use the measurements to profile the application code and to extract insights that help the programmer.

At the Irish Center for High-End Computing (ICHEC), we have developed a System for Energy Measurement on Accelerators (SEMA) that allows measurement of any accelerator or any number of them to an accuracy of milliwatt and a resolution of millisecond. SEMA works based on the standard current shunt-based power measurement technique. Such a methodology is not new and there has been prior work done within a lab environment. SEMA embarks to be different and we focus equally on usability as much as technical feasibility. To meet this endeavor, we have come up with set of novel ideas that abstract the technical details and provide the users with a very simple interface to measure energy and power. This interface can also be used to profile very short regions of code within the application. This allows extraction of insights into the performance and power consumption of different pieces of code at a level not possible before, thereby leading to improvements in understanding the code behavior and optimizations. These can also be fed back to the design of better energy efficient accelerator architectures in the future.

The current SEMA system is capable of performing power measurements on three different accelerators within a single system. However, we need to expand this system to work in a cluster environment in order to test large parallel applications. This requires improving the SEMA hardware with better integration into the host system and better programming infrastructure to manage the myriad of sensors. In the future, we hope such a system could be integrated as a standard interface in supercomputing clusters.

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1. Motivation

The dominance of accelerators for energy efficient computing in HPC clusters makes it essential to utilize them effectively. It has increasingly become crucial to understand the relationship between their power consumption, performance and application code in order to exploit them in an effective manner. The measurement of power consumption of these devices is supported at different levels of accuracy by different vendors through their platforms. However, they lack any standardized metrics between them making it difficult to compare them directly. Furthermore, the accuracy supported by these existing mechanisms is at a coarse level making it impossible to use the measurements to profile the application at a finer timescale. System for Energy Measurement on Accelerators or SEMA is a combination of current sensors, measurement interface and an application library for power measurement of various PCIe accelerators.

2. Introduction

SEMA was designed with two main goals, one being cost effective to implement and two to provide easy access to energy measurement for software programmers. SEMA works based on the standard current shunt-based power measurement technique. SEMA focuses on usability and technical feasibility by abstracting the finer details and provides the users with a very simple interface to measure energy and power. This interface can be used to profile even very short regions of code within the application. SEMA supports current generation accelerators predominantly used in HPC clusters such as NVIDIA GPGPUs and Intel Xeon Phi. SEMA can provide the European HPC community with valuable data on the relationship of applications and accelerators in the endeavour to achieve energy efficient Exascale computing.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: We present the overall system design in section 3, software library in section 4, initial results in section 5, related work in section 6 and finally conclusion in section 7.

3. System Design

Accelerators draw power from both the PCIe rail from the motherboard and through external connector from the power supply. Two different voltages are supplied from the motherboard which are 3.3V and 12V. The external connectors supply 12V. While most of the power drawn is from the external connector, a significant amount is supplied from the motherboard as well. Each of these individual power supply lines are referred to as voltage rails. To calculate power consumption accurately, it is essential to be able to introduce a mechanism through which current flow can be measured at any given time on the various voltage rails. In Figure 1, the overall system diagram is shown. An NVIDIA Tesla K40 and an Intel Xeon Phi 7120 were chosen for the initial evaluation of the system.

Figure 1. Overall System Design

3.1 Current Sensor

Energy consumed is measured by the amount of power consumed by a device over a given period of time. While devices are able to handle a maximum power handling capability specified as its Thermal Design Power (TDP), the actual power consumed at any given instance can vary due to a variety of reasons such as clock frequency,

sleep state, memory accessed. Therefore, it is important to be able to measure the power being drawn by these devices rather than rely on the TDP to be able to calculate the energy consumed accurately.

In a lab environment, current is measured using an instrument known as Ammeter. This is connected in series with the supply voltage of the device being tested and measures the current drawn instantaneously. Ammeters work by connecting a current shunt resistor in the path of the current flow. This introduces a voltage drop proportional to the flow of current in accordance with “Ohm’s Law” across the resistor. Using an Analog to Digital Converter (ADC), it makes it possible to read the voltage drop across this resistor. Since the resistance value is known, we can precisely calculate the current in the circuit.

An ammeter’s measurement accuracy is limited by the front-end or the ADC. Therefore, to cater to the variety of scenarios as a general purpose meter, different shunt resistors are used to measure the current in multiple fixed ranges. Higher current ranges require very small resistance value and vice-versa for lower ranges.

Power consumption on the supply rails to PCIe accelerators can vary through a wide range on a general purpose ammeter, making it difficult to accurately measure the current drawn. Also, using multiple resistances and switching between them can interrupt the current flow, which in turn might affect the operational capability of the device being tested.

Since PCIe accelerators operate over a known range, we could use purpose-built power measurement sensors that are designed to accurately measure current, voltage and calculate power. These sensors work using the same principle as an ammeter but they use a very small resistance value and are matched for a fixed range as specified in its datasheet. Moreover, the built-in ADC of these sensors support high sampling and averaging techniques that can take measurements faster than a general purpose ammeter. They also support the ability to control, read and store various measurements through digital interfaces.

In a HPC system, the current consumption of accelerators varies from few milliamps (mA) to a few amps (A). The voltage being measured is mostly a constant value of 12V or 3.3V with very small variations. INA226 [1] from Texas Instruments (TI) is able to handle the specified range and is also one of industry’s best current measurement sensor. The measurement setup for a single power rail is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Current measurement interface with INA226 sensor

3.2 PCIe Interposer

It is relatively easy to connect the sensor board inline with external power connectors. However, to be able to precisely measure power being drawn from the motherboard, a device known as the PCIe Interposer is required. The interposer essentially sits between the physical PCIe connector and the accelerator being measured. It reroutes the power rails coming from the motherboard through external traces which, if needed, can be used to connect a different source to power the card. Since we were interested only in the power rails from the motherboard, we used Adex Electronics “PEXP16-EX” extender shown in Figure 3 with an external power input connection [2].

Figure 3. Adex Electronics PCIe extender with external power connector

We chose to go with prefabricated sensor boards based on the INA226 from Tinkerforge [3] shown in Figure 4. Each sensor board is able to handle a maximum power draw of 720W or 20A of current. However, since the power delivered to the card comes from different connectors of the power supply, we use five of these sensor boards per card. Two of them are dedicated to the 12V and 3.3V coming from the motherboard. One of them is for the external six pin connector and two of them are for the eight pin connector which provide external 12V supply.

A single microcontroller board [4] is used to read the values from four sensor boards. The sensor boards are configured to sample and produce an average reading of current, voltage and power once every 2-3 milliseconds. The microcontroller board is used to read the values and interfaced with the computer over USB. In the host system, these sensors are polled at regular intervals to capture their measurements.

Figure 4. Tinkerforge Bricklet - INA226 sensor board

4. Software Library

The sensors support APIs provided by Tinkerforge for reading the instantaneous current, voltage and power measurements [5]. However, this requires constant polling from the host to read each of the sensor values. Since we have almost ten sensors to read from, we developed a parallel measurement and interface library on top of the APIs provided for these sensors. This library consists of two parts, the first which creates several background threads to handle various functions. For every sensor whose values need to be measured, a separate polling thread is created to continuously fetch the value. A storage thread delegates the process of combining the individual measurement values into a single power and energy measurement reading for each accelerator. Finally, a master thread updates an internal counter with this value and derives metrics such as peak power for the duration of the run.

The second part of the library consists of interface APIs which are used to instrument regions of the host code where power measurements are required. Since the sensors are read in the same host where the application is executed on the accelerator, we are able to correlate the measured energy with even small portions of the code. In Listing 1, we show an example with the APIs to measure the power of the GPU.

```

#include "sema.h"

void main( int argc, char *argv[] )
{
    SEMA.Initialize( GPU );
    double e_rtime = 0.0, e_energy = 0.0, e_rtime_tot = 0.0, e_energy_tot = 0.0;
    double peak_power_t = 0.0, peak_power = 0.0, peak_power_a = 0.0;
    int i;
    for( i = 0; i < 2; i++ )
    {
        SEMA.Start();
        sleep( 3 );
        SEMA.Stop();
        SEMA.Get( &e_rtime, &e_energy, &peak_power_t );
        printf( "RTIME=%.2f ENERGY=%.2f PEAK_POWER=%.2f\n", e_rtime, e_energy, peak_power_t );
    }
    SEMA.Finalize();
}

```

Listing 1. SEMA library user interface example

In the listing, “SEMA.Initialize()” is used to set the measured device to be either the “GPU” or “PHI” for Tesla K40 or Xeon Phi 7120, respectively. “SEMA.Start()” and “SEMA.Stop()” are used around regions of the code to take measurements. “SEMA.Get()” is used to read the program runtime, energy and peak power internal counters of the SEMA library. Finally, “SEMA.Finalize()” stops the background threads and resets any of the internal storage used for the counters. The whole interface is designed to be dynamically linkable with simple and easy access to necessary APIs. This minimises the overhead introduced by the instrumentation.

5. Initial Results

We have setup a few initial experiments to evaluate our system. This mainly consists of a few native codes running on two accelerators and a benchmark that can run on either of these devices. In this evaluation, our objective is not to optimize the code for a particular device but to present results that can be used as a starting point for further analysis.

The two accelerators chosen for our system are the NVIDIA Tesla K40 and Intel Xeon Phi 7120. The Tesla K40 comes with 6GB RAM and 2880 threading cores. It can run at a maximum frequency of 875 MHz and is designed for a TDP of 235 Watts. Its capable of ~4 TF/s in single precision, ~1.5 TF/s in double precision operations and has a maximum memory bandwidth of ~288 GB/s. The Intel Xeon Phi 7120 has 61 cores and 16GB of memory and can run at a maximum frequency of 1.33 GHz in turbo mode with a designed TDP of 300 Watts. It is capable of ~2.4 TF/s in single precision, ~1.2 TF/s in double precision operations and ~352 GB/s of peak memory bandwidth.

These accelerators are widely used in large supercomputing clusters in the PRACE consortium to achieve several Petaflops of performance. Improvements on performance and energy efficiency of these devices would greatly impact the European scientific communities leading to effective use of their HPC resources.

The initial results consist of measurements on the two devices with different benchmarks. In Figure 5 and Figure 6, we present a few initial results on the Intel Xeon Phi 7120. The X-axis consists of different types of measurement performed on the same program marked by ‘xN’ where ‘N’ is the factor multiplied with the value in Y-axis. Each item in the X-axis also contains variations such as the type of precision used or the kind of operation performed.

Figure 5 shows a general matrix multiplication (GEMM) based on OpenMP running on the Phi. We have two metrics for performance derived from execution time of the code within the benchmark and from the counter within SEMA interface. We find that there is a slight overhead for the performance metric by measuring it using the SEMA library in comparison to within the code. We can also see the energy efficiency result represented by GFlops/J and the peak power represented in ‘W’ or Watts. It is observed that even though only a slight increase in peak power is seen when switching from single to double precision, the energy efficiency actually drops in half.

Figure 5. Intel Xeon Phi 7120 - GEMM with OMP parallelism baseline results

Figure 6. Intel Xeon Phi 7120 - Unoptimized ViennaCL - 1.7.1

In Figure 6, an unoptimized version of ViennaCL [6] was executed in the Phi. It compares different GEMM operations. The prefix corresponds to the precision used 's' for single and 'd' for double. The suffix corresponds to whether the matrix was transposed before the GEMM operation. 'NN' corresponds to normal GEMM, 'NT' corresponds to the second matrix being transposed, 'TN' corresponds to first matrix being transposed and 'TT' corresponds to both matrix being transposed. A similar trend to Figure 5 can be seen here. The peak power varies marginally between the runs. For these measurements the trend between the performance and energy efficiency is quite similar as well.

Figure 7. NVIDIA Tesla K40c CUDA NBody results

In Figure 7, we present the results of a CUDA benchmark optimized on the NVIDIA Tesla K40. In contrast to the timing discrepancy observed in the Intel Xeon Phi results, the performance results obtained by the counters within the SEMA interface correlated with those measured within the program. On further investigation, we found that there is a slight overhead with the Intel OpenMP library used and the measurements for performance by the benchmark excludes this. Figure 7 shows a similar trend we observed in the Xeon Phi results where the peak power doesn't necessarily correlate with the energy efficiency measurement. It can also be observed the Tesla K40 does appear to be more efficient in the NBody operation in comparison to that of GEMM operation does in the Xeon Phi. Since both the accelerators are measured using the same experimental system, it is possible to even compare energy efficiency of two different operations across devices.

Figure 8. NVIDIA Tesla K40 - Optimized ViennaCL - 1.7.1

In Figure 8, we present results from an optimized version of ViennaCL for the GEMM operation on the Tesla K40. It compares different GEMM operations. The prefix corresponds to the precision used 's' for single and 'd' for double. The suffix corresponds to whether the matrix was transposed before the GEMM operation. 'NN' corresponds to normal GEMM, 'NT' corresponds to the second matrix being transposed, 'TN' corresponds to

first matrix being transposed and ‘TT’ corresponds to both matrix being transposed. Two interesting observations comparing performance and energy efficiency can be made. While the “sGEMM-NT” and “sGEMM-TT” provide similar performances, it can be observed that “sGEMM-NT” is in fact slightly more energy efficiency in comparison to “sGEMM-TT”. In the case of double precision, the “dGEMM-TN” and “dGEMM-TT” are similar in energy efficiency while their performances differ significantly.

6. Related Work

PowerMon [7], WattProf and PowerInsight [8] are hardware cards used for measurement of the current consumption of various devices. SEMA is more focused on the ease of energy measurements and through its software library enables fairly accurate correlation with the application code.

Performance API (PAPI) analysis library supports energy measurement through vendor specific systems such as Intel RAPL hardware counters [9]. The Energy Measurement Library (EML) [10] provides a uniform interface to a diverse set of power measurement tools. SEMA differs from the PAPI library by means of dedicated data acquisition threads that are specifically used for high-speed capture of the sensor data. This slightly offsets the measurement capabilities from hardware to software making SEMA more flexible in the rate at which data can be measured. SEMA doesn’t strive to be an interface to other measurement tools like EML, but rather aims to be a complete system consisting of a lightweight library and hardware power measurement sensors.

7. Conclusion

Accelerators form the basis of performance and energy efficient computing in many supercomputing clusters in the world including several of them in Europe compute centres. Understanding the relationship of performance and energy efficiency of these devices would greatly help the European scientific communities to effectively utilize these resources. SEMA, through the basis of its hardware platform and software library, forms an essential tool for application developers. SEMA is able to facilitate accurate correlation of energy consumed and the code executed thereby providing insight into effective optimisations suitable for these devices.

8. References

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